

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT OF NEOPHYTE TEACHERS: A MIXED-METHOD STUDY

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Classroom Management of Neophyte Teachers: A Mixed-Method Study

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Abstract

Studies shown that early years of teaching are widely recognized as the most difficult for newly graduated educators. This study investigated the classroom management skills of neophyte teachers in selected public elementary schools in Davao del Norte from the perspective of their students. A mixed-method design with a parallel convergent approach was employed. Participants included elementary students from grades 4 to 6, under the instruction of neophyte teachers. A total of 122 students were randomly chosen for the quantitative part, while 10 students were selected for the qualitative aspect: five participated in in-depth interviews and five in focus group discussions, chosen through purposive sampling. For the quantitative analysis, descriptive statistics like the mean were used to assess the average responses, and standard deviation was employed to measure the variability of students' responses regarding their teachers' classroom management practices. In the qualitative analysis, participant responses were transcribed, organized, and coded to identify themes. The study found that the overall level of classroom management among neophyte teachers was high. While no significant difference was observed in classroom management practices based on the students' sex, there was a significant difference based on grade level. The quantitative and qualitative findings aligned when compared, confirming that despite initial challenges, neophyte teachers can exhibit strong classroom management skills that foster structured, supportive, and engaging environments, benefiting students both academically and personally.

Keywords: *classroom management, neophyte teachers, elementary students, public schools*

Introduction

The early years of teaching are widely recognized as the most difficult for newly graduated educators. The shift from teacher education programs to actual classroom environments is often described as a form of reality shock, where new teachers realize that the concepts they learned during their training may not fully align with the difficulties they face during their initial year of teaching. Many neophytes feel underprepared to handle the difficulties they face in their initial years in the classroom (Hachelef & Chami, 2020).

In Turkey, managing the classroom has consistently been a challenge for neophyte teachers, particularly when addressing disruptive student behaviors such as bullying, excessive talking, interrupting, being noisy, leaving their seats without a valid reason, using inappropriate language, and showing disobedience or disrespect towards the teacher. New teachers expressed frustration over their inability to foresee misbehavior, their ineffective strategies for handling it, and their lack of expertise in managing such situations (Sali & Kecik, 2018).

In Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines, neophyte teachers found classroom management to be one of the most difficult aspects of their initial year of teaching. According to the researcher, these beginner teachers generally struggle to manage students effectively in their initial year, which has led to some student misbehaviors being unintentionally overlooked (Candilas, 2018).

Effective classroom management is often considered one of the most critical actions a teacher can take for their students. It helps in creating a positive, productive, and engaging learning environment that benefits both teachers and students by promoting respect, responsibility, and collaboration, ultimately leading to better academic outcomes and the overall well-being of everyone in the classroom. This study seeks to determine if teaching experience is linked to the classroom management skills of neophyte teachers using a mixed-method research approach. The findings could offer valuable insights, providing a deeper understanding of the challenges and strategies involved. This, in turn, could inform the development of better educational policies, teacher training programs, and support systems to improve the effectiveness and well-being of new teachers in managing their classrooms.

Classroom management of neophyte teachers has been tackled on numerous studies, like the study of Nabil et al. (2021) entitled "The Experiences of Neophyte Teachers: Meeting the Challenges of the First Professional Practices", and the study of Candilas (2018) entitled "21st Century Neophyte Teachers' Lived Experiences in Teaching: A Phenomenological Study", both studies focused on the experiences of neophyte teachers which includes classroom management as one of the incessant difficulties that neophyte teachers encountered. This study differs to the studies that have mentioned as this study specifically investigated the classroom management among neophyte teachers in Davao del Norte, which is still less explored in the body of knowledge. Copies of the study will be disseminated to the various research conferences and concerned agencies to facilitate scholarly exchange and utilization of research-based discovery.

Research Questions

This study investigates the classroom management of neophyte teachers using a mixed method research approach. The purpose of employing this approach was to gather both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, merge the findings, and utilize them to

address the research problem at hand. This research design allowed for the strengths of each data collection method to offset the limitations of the other, resulting in a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem through the combined analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data.

1. What is the level of classroom management of the neophyte teachers?
2. What is the significant difference of the level of classroom management among neophyte teachers when grouped according to sex and grade level?
3. What are the experiences of the elementary students with regards to their neophyte teachers' classroom management?
4. To what degree do the quantitative data corroborate with qualitative data?

Literature Review

In the context of Philippine education, creating an effective and inclusive learning environment is critical to student success. According to the Department of Education (DepEd) Memorandum, maintaining optimal classroom conditions is essential for fostering an environment that promotes effective teaching and learning (DepEd, 2016). A classroom's physical condition, discipline strategies, routines, and time management are all integral components that impact both the academic performance and well-being of learners. Studies have shown that these factors, when carefully managed and optimized, foster an environment conducive to learning, engagement, and positive behavior. This literature review explores these key aspects of classroom management, focusing on the influence of the physical classroom environment, the importance of clear routines and discipline, and effective time management in supporting student achievement. By drawing on both local and international research, this review highlights best practices for creating classrooms that promote both academic success and social-emotional growth.

Classroom Physical Condition

The physical condition of a classroom or any learning space significantly impacts both the social dynamics and the learning potential of students. It's not just the psychological atmosphere that influences students, but the tangible, physical aspects of the space as well. For instance, when a classroom is overcrowded, poorly lit, or damp, it creates an unfavorable setting that can hinder a student's learning process and negatively affect their mental well-being. An optimal physical environment is crucial in promoting effective learning and supporting students' mental health. Thus, physical classroom setting is vital in fostering a conducive and healthy educational experience (Paul & Kumari, 2018).

Moreover, the physical condition of a classroom refers to its various characteristics, such as the size of the room, the flooring, walls, desks, lighting, overall school structure, climate, and the availability of technology like computers. The quality of these physical elements plays a crucial role in influencing students' academic performance. Well-equipped classrooms help in establishing an environment that fosters an effective and successful teaching and learning process. Without these essential facilities, the learning experience may be hindered. In a well-facilitated classroom, students are more likely to engage with their instructors and perform better academically. Conversely, if the classroom environment is uncomfortable or poorly arranged, students may struggle to focus and become easily distracted, negatively affecting their attention to the lesson (Mustapha & Abulfathi, 2019).

A study has identified a relationship between the physical setup of a classroom—including factors like room layout, space size, lighting, and table arrangement—and psychological aspects such as teacher-student and peer interactions. The organization of these physical features can either facilitate or obstruct interaction and affect expected behaviors in the classroom. The research also highlighted that the physical environment influences the comfort level of both teaching and learning. Key contributors to this comfort include furniture, space, and air quality. Therefore, careful planning of the classroom's physical elements is essential to support educational objectives and meet learners' needs (Puteh et al., 2018).

In addition, the classroom plays a critical role as the primary environment for school-aged children, making it essential to fully understand its composition in order to make informed decisions that foster inclusion and engagement. To create an optimal learning space, several key elements of the physical classroom environment must be considered. These include ambient factors like temperature, acoustics, odor, and air quality, as well as the spatial layout, which encompasses the seating arrangement, available equipment, and furnishings. Additionally, the presence of signs, symbols, and artifacts within the space contributes to the overall atmosphere. These aspects are especially important in light of the growing emphasis on creating classrooms that prioritize inclusion and acceptance, ensuring that all students feel supported and engaged (Brannstrom et al., 2021).

Teachers must recognize the diversity of their students' needs and adjust the physical classroom condition just as they would adapt a lesson plan to meet different learning styles. The physical setup of the classroom is just as crucial to student success as the curriculum itself and cannot be overlooked. A teacher's understanding and approach to these environmental factors significantly influence how students engage with the material and interact with one another.

If a student is struggling to learn within the current classroom setting, it is the teacher's duty to rethink and modify the environment to create a space that better supports the student's learning needs. By being flexible and responsive in adjusting the physical conditions of the classroom, educators can create more inclusive, comfortable, and effective learning spaces that allow every student to thrive (Beyer, 2020).

Classroom Discipline

Discipline issues present challenges for most neophyte teachers and even some experienced educators. Effective managing of classroom, paired with a solid discipline plan, helps reduce disruptive behavior so the class can stay focused on learning. Discipline begins with the teacher; therefore, each class session should start with a positive attitude and high expectations. Teachers can display a discipline plan that they will consistently follow to regulate student behavior. Research indicates that teachers who are consistent and fair tend to have successful classroom management. If teachers overlook disruptions one day but enforce rules strictly the next, students may not take them seriously. This inconsistency can lead to a loss of respect and increased disruptions. Additionally, if rules are enforced unfairly, students are likely to feel resentment (Kelly, 2019).

At its core, effective classroom discipline relies on three key skills: motivating students, addressing inappropriate behavior, and sustaining discipline once it is established. In reality, classroom management often differs from what most first-year teachers anticipate. Many envision themselves leading a harmonious, ideal classroom where all students respect each other and follow their guidance. However, children are not adults and require direction; they cannot be expected to instinctively know how to behave and adapt to the classroom environment. It is the teacher's duty to create and maintain this learning environment (Flaherty et al., 2023).

Additionally, managing classroom discipline can be challenging for teachers alongside their other responsibilities, such as administrative tasks, adhering to the curriculum, and keeping up with current classroom trends. Developing specific behavioral and academic plans can assist teachers in staying focused and achieving their educational objectives as the year progresses. However, this requires considerable effort and support from administrators, parents, and other educational professionals. Often, engaging lessons can effectively motivate students and help manage their behavior. However, in some instances, students may require additional support to address behavioral issues and foster a growth mindset (Hegwood, 2023).

Classroom rules are essential for maintaining discipline, and ensuring adherence to these rules is vital. A quantitative study was conducted to examine the expectations of the students regarding rule in the classroom. The findings indicate that students expect rules to be set at the beginning of the school year, prefer to have a role in creating these rules, and wish for minimal alterations thereafter. They also anticipate a limited number of rules and expect teachers to reinforce positive behavior. Moreover, the study revealed that students are more inclined to adhere to rules in a tidy, uncrowded setting and prefer that their parents are not informed about these rules. The results imply that stronger compliance with classroom rules fosters greater inclusion in the class, while weaker compliance reduces it. Additionally, implementing classroom rules leads to enhanced class cohesion, whereas not having rules results in diminished cohesion (Demir et al., 2023).

Furthermore, a study revealed that teachers emphasized the importance of clearly establishing and enforcing classroom rules during in-person lessons to promote student adherence. They reported using a range of classroom management strategies to uphold these regulations. In this context, both teachers and students must strictly adhere to the established rules in face-to-face classes. The rules must be clear, straightforward, vital, and easily enforceable (Maureal & Villajos, 2023).

Moreover, classroom teachers are tasked with delivering efficient instruction to many students at once. Whenever students exhibit problematic behaviors, it can negatively affect both instructional quality and time. To maintain classroom discipline, a study highlights the effectiveness of multiple reinforcement schedules in reducing problem behaviors, demonstrating its efficacy across various educational settings with diverse student populations. A multiple schedule of reinforcement is a behavioral intervention technique that allows educators to clarify the specific situations in which certain behaviors will receive reinforcement or not. This strategy includes pinpointing disruptive behaviors that happen too often or at inappropriate moments and communicating to students when positive behaviors will be rewarded and when they will not (through clear signals). Once educators comprehend the methods and applications, they are well-prepared to utilize multiple schedules in various educational environments (Vargo, 2020).

Care of Routine

A routine creates a structured environment, clearly informing students about what to expect, what is expected of them, and what constitutes acceptable behavior. It enables students to efficiently complete daily tasks that are important for both the teacher and the students. Routines facilitate smoother transitions between activities, reducing opportunities for disruptions. Additionally, routines that require communication between the teacher and students or among students promote positive interpersonal communication and social skills, serving as a way for teachers to assess the quality and quantity of students' abilities in these areas (Burden, 2020).

Routines are practiced responses to a teacher's instructions. In contrast, a lack of routines often results in students complaining, yelling, and wasting time, forcing the teacher to repeatedly regain control of the classroom throughout the school year. Research indicates that effective routines help teachers save time while still offering a valuable learning experience for students. However, it's important for educators not to present routines as a hindrance to students. When students enjoy their daily routines, they are much more likely to internalize the key concepts the teacher aims to teach through those routines (Malak, 2022).

Moreover, a study highlights that a key component of an effective routine is establishing a straightforward and clear sequence of actions, with the first student task being easily achievable with little effort. Each routine needs a signal to indicate its beginning. These signals should be clear, brief, and utilize multiple modes; for example, by pairing a verbal instruction with a non-verbal gesture from

a designated area in the classroom. Routines must be explicitly taught, regularly reinforced, and sustained to ensure that the processes become automatic before the learning benefits can be achieved (Mccrea, 2020).

Furthermore, research indicates that teaching routines and procedures is essential for developing good skills and behaviors. Habits and routines often originate at home. Classroom routines and procedures are established to maintain order within the classroom. By staying focused on tasks, following directions, and remaining seated unless otherwise instructed, students can maximize their learning time. There will always be work available for students to complete, which helps cultivate positive skills and behaviors from the outset of their education (Rumulus, 2021).

Teachers continuously refine their skills through ongoing learning, practical experience, and self-reflection. Routines, which are short, purposeful sequences of teacher actions within a lesson, are essential to this development. These sequences of behavior are particularly evident in German geography classes. A study was conducted to examine what routines look like in the everyday teaching practices of geography teachers, analyzing the collected data through frequency analysis. The results reveal that the observed teachers exhibit consistent patterns of routine during specific phases of the lesson, including their use of teaching methods, materials, media, and classroom management (Krohmer & Budke, 2021).

Additionally, research suggests that teachers experience greater success in managing students when clear goals, boundaries, and expectations that prioritize respect and responsibility are established. A key principle of classroom management is establishing clear expectations. Students thrive in environments with clear boundaries and consistent routines, as this helps them understand what is expected of them throughout the school day. Therefore, outlining behavior expectations is crucial. By clearly communicating what you want students to achieve, you can guide them on how to succeed, which minimizes the time spent addressing behavioral issues during lessons (Williams, 2019).

Time Management

Time is defined as the duration in which a task or event occurs, is expected to occur, or is currently occurring. The effective and efficient use of time is crucial for individuals to take control of their lives and reach their goals. The teaching profession relies heavily on planned work and the ability to manage time effectively. Teachers face unique time-related challenges, such as completing lesson content on schedule and engaging with students at the appropriate times, which can create pressure. Consequently, mastering time management skills allows teachers to achieve their objectives more efficiently. It's essential for teachers to develop these skills during their education so they can effectively manage time in their professional roles (Eskimen, 2023).

Furthermore, a study underscores the importance of time management as a cornerstone of effective classroom management. Teachers who master time management techniques experience enhanced focus and efficiency, allowing them to maintain momentum and complete tasks more swiftly. Recognizing the finite nature of time, teachers seeking career advancement must prioritize time management strategies. Whether they employ time-chunking methods or rely on list-making, effective time management empowers teachers to make more informed decisions (Olivo, 2021).

One strategy for managing time is to organize daily activities. Effective time management for teachers begins with prioritizing and structuring the day around the most critical tasks. Additionally, planning homework strategically is important. Setting priorities helps teachers stay focused throughout the day, even when unexpected challenges arise and the workload feels overwhelming. Effective prioritization involves arranging tasks based on their importance and the impact of their completion. Teachers need to evaluate whether certain projects can be postponed if their outcomes are less significant than others (Chong, 2019).

Additionally, researchers investigated the connection between teachers' awareness of time and student academic achievement in public elementary schools. A descriptive research design was utilized, guided by two research questions and corresponding hypotheses. The findings indicate that lesson planning, delivery, and student assessment require significant attention in teachers' time management, as there is a strong link between teachers' time awareness and students' academic performance. Therefore, it recommends, among other measures, that teachers receive training in effective time planning and that their workload be reduced to enhance academic excellence (Roberts & Moses, 2022).

Moreover, effective classroom management hinges on a teacher's ability to design and deliver engaging lessons that minimize distractions, boredom, and misbehavior. Successful teachers craft well-structured, well-paced lessons that flow smoothly, minimizing confusion and distractions. They efficiently transition students between activities and provide seatwork that aligns with students' abilities and interests (Afalla & Fabelico, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a mixed methods design, combining both qualitative and quantitative components to offer a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. Halcomb and Hickman (2015) emphasize that integrating these components is crucial for ensuring the rigor of mixed methods research, with the integration occurring at any stage of the process. "Mixing" refers to the process of linking the qualitative and quantitative elements for a more holistic view of the issue. Bryman (2007) highlights that mixed methods

research goes beyond simple validation by combining different approaches, leading to a deeper and more multifaceted understanding of the topic. This approach not only confirms findings but also uncovers new insights that may not be apparent with a single-method approach.

This study utilized a convergent parallel mixed-methods design, collecting both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, with equal emphasis placed on each. Surveys were collected first, followed by either focus group discussions or individual interviews. The two data sets were analyzed independently before being integrated, allowing for a combined interpretation of the results. This design was chosen to explore possible convergence, divergence, contradictions, or relationships between the data sources (Hanson et al., 2005).

The convergent parallel design, also known as the triangulation design, combines quantitative and qualitative methods within a single phase of the study, giving both methods equal importance. The data collection and analysis are conducted independently, but the results are merged during the final interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

This research utilized a combined approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative methods through a convergent parallel design to gain a comprehensive understanding of the topic. The convergent parallel design, as described by Morse (1991), involves conducting both types of research concurrently in the same phase, with equal emphasis on each. The data are analyzed independently before being integrated to form a complete interpretation. The study's conclusions are strengthened by examining both numerical data and detailed observations side-by-side, seeking points of agreement or disagreement (Demir & Pismek, 2018).

In this study, a convergent parallel design was employed to analyze both qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously. Qualitative data, such as screen recordings and transcriptions, were collected alongside quantitative data from a survey questionnaire. The qualitative data were analyzed through discourse and thematic analysis to explore the experiences of students taught by neophyte educators regarding classroom management. The quantitative data were analyzed using statistical methods to examine student profiles, their experiences, and any significant differences in perceptions. This analysis also aimed to determine how well the quantitative findings aligned with the qualitative insights, providing a comprehensive understanding of the students' experiences.

This research used a descriptive-comparative approach to analyze and compare the results, drawing meaningful conclusions about neophyte teachers' classroom management. It utilized both quantitative and qualitative methods to deepen the understanding of effective teaching strategies (Richardson, 2018). To enhance the qualitative framework, a phenomenological approach was employed, focusing on exploring shared experiences among the participants. This approach typically involves interviews with individuals who have direct knowledge of an event, with additional data sources like documents and observations incorporated to enrich the findings (Creswell, 2013).

The qualitative aspect of this research employed a phenomenological lens, emphasizing the existence of diverse subjective realities. Data was gathered through qualitative methods like focus group discussions and individual interviews. These methods were instrumental in uncovering the community's social norms, enriching the data from in-depth interviews, and identifying key themes derived from the researcher's observations (Groenewald, 2004).

Participants

The respondents of this study were the elementary students from grades 4 (four) to six (6) who are under the instruction of neophyte teachers or teachers with one (1) year teaching experience in selected public schools in Davao del Norte. The study participants were selected because they are the primary individuals who directly experience the classroom management techniques of neophyte teachers. Their perspectives towards the classroom management of their teachers provide valuable insights of the level of classroom management among neophyte teachers.

Further, the respondents were determined through sampling, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This approach entails segmenting the population into distinct subgroups, known as "strata," and then randomly choosing a representative sample from each of these subgroups. The per-stratum samples are then combined to create an overall stratified random sample. Instead of selecting participants purely by chance, stratified random sampling divides the population into distinct groups, or strata. This method guarantees that each group is proportionally represented in the sample, leading to more precise insights when analyzing specific subgroups within the overall population (Nguyen et al., 2020).

The chosen sampling method was well-suited to the specific aims of this research because the respondents, which are the elementary students under the instruction of neophyte teachers or teachers with one (1) year teaching experience was randomly selected based on strata, which in this case are students from grades 4 (four) to six (6) in selected public schools in Davao del Norte. This approach guarantees that every individual within the target group has an equal opportunity to be chosen for participation. The researcher formally requested permission from the School Principals of the selected public elementary schools and gained access to the population of students under the instruction of neophyte teachers from grades 4 (four) to six (6). The researcher then gathered the data from the population of elementary students from grades 4 (four) to six (6) who are under the instruction of neophyte teachers to compute the sample. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to her statistician for computation of the study sample.

The study was conducted among grades 4 (four) to six (6) students who are under the instruction of neophyte teachers in selected public

schools in Davao del Norte. The selected public schools have a total of 178 students, consisting of 30 male and 42 female students from Mangkay Integrated School, 12 male and 19 female students from Gupitan Integrated School, 30 male and 34 female students from Magbaad Elementary School, and 5 male and 6 female students from Mahayahay Elementary School. However, the sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician, which included 21 out of 30 male students and 29 out of 42 female students from Mangkay Integrated School, 8 out of 12 male students and 13 out of 19 female students from Gupitan Integrated School, 21 out of 30 male students and 23 out of 34 female students from Magbaad Elementary School, and 3 out of 5 male students and 4 out of 6 female students from Mahayahay Elementary School. In total, 122 students were sampled out of the 178 students from grades 4 (four) to six (6) who are under the instruction of neophyte teachers.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>School</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Mangkay IS (Male)	30	21	12%
Mangkay IS (Female)	42	29	16%
Gupitan IS (Male)	12	8	5%
Gupitan IS (Female)	19	13	7%
Magbaad ES (Male)	30	21	12%
Magbaad ES (Female)	34	23	13%
Mahayahay ES (Male)	5	3	2%
Mahayahay ES (Female)	6	4	2%
Total	178	122	69%

Qualitative Phase

Qualitative research employed a deliberate approach to participant selection, prioritizing individuals who could provide the most insightful information. This method, known as purposive sampling, aimed to ensure that the chosen participants possessed the knowledge and experiences necessary to shed light on the research questions and deepen the understanding of the phenomenon being investigated (Kuper et al., 2008). Only 10 participants of elementary students will be enjoined in the qualitative phase: five (5) for in-depth interview and another five (5) for focus group discussion. All of them should be elementary students from grades 4 (four) to six (6) who are under neophyte teachers or teachers with one (1) year teaching experience in public schools in Davao del Norte. It should be noted that participants in qualitative phase must not have participated in the data collection of quantitative phases.

Table 1.2. *Profiles of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Female	Grade 5
IDI-02	Male	Grade 6
IDI-03	Female	Grade 6
IDI-04	Male	Grade 6
IDI-05	Female	Grade 6
FGD-01	Male	Grade 5
FGD-02	Female	Grade 5
FGD-03	Female	Grade 5
FGD-04	Male	Grade 4
FGD-05	Female	Grade 4

Instrument

Quantitative Phase

The researcher utilized an adapted survey questionnaire for teachers' classroom management practices which was adapted from Afalla and Fabelico (2020). The said questionnaire used a Five-point Likert Scale which had the following indicators: the following indicators: classroom management condition, classroom discipline, care of routine, and time management.

A five-point Likert scale was employed for data collection, where respondents indicated their agreement or disagreement with each statement by selecting a single option from a range of one to five, with one representing the lowest level of agreement and five representing the highest. This type of scale is particularly effective for gauging constructs, attitudes, and stimuli that are not directly observable. While the questionnaire underwent adaptation, it was further subjected to expert review for validation.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions was devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that was developed based on the results of the survey. This was used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. Of all the participants who answered the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, five were purposively selected to undergo the IDI and another five for the FGD. Interviews were suitable in gleaning insights, stories, experiences, opinions and other useful information which could not be expressed with the use of numbers.

Procedure

The data collection process involved a series of distinct stages. The study employed the following methods:

Quantitative Phase

To gather data on classroom management practices among neophyte teachers, a modified survey was distributed to elementary students taught by these teachers. The researcher also sought permission from school administrators at the chosen public schools to conduct the study. This involved obtaining approval to access the school and its students. The survey results were compiled, calculated, and analyzed to confirm the findings from the qualitative data. Both the qualitative and quantitative aspects of the research were carried out concurrently.

Qualitative Phase

To delve deeper into the qualitative aspect of the study, one-on-one interviews were conducted with the chosen participants. The aim was to gain insights into their personal experiences with elementary students being taught by neophyte teachers, specifically focusing on the teachers' classroom management practices. A structured interview guide was used for both the in-depth interview and the focus group discussion. To ensure the participants' genuine involvement, the researcher personally contacted them, explaining the study's objectives and the tasks involved, including flexible scheduling to accommodate everyone's availability (Creswell, 2013).

The focus group discussion centered on the exploration of individuals' opinions, experiences, concerns, and desires regarding the specific issues at hand. According to Traynor's (2015), this method typically involves gathering a selected group of people with shared characteristic, guided by a researcher, to participate in open discussions. The goal is to foster a collaborative environment where participants can share their viewpoints, recount personal experiences, and offer valuable insights on a specific topic. A key element of this methodology is the deliberate focus on interaction and group dynamics. The discussions took various forms, including one-on-one sessions, and were recorded through screen recording, with additional notes taken.

Additionally, individual and in-depth interviews offered a unique platform to delve into the perspectives of elementary students on how they perceived the classroom management styles of their neophyte teachers. Ten (10) students were purposively selected for these interviews, which were conducted by the researcher.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of the elementary students under neophyte teachers from selected public schools in Davao del Norte, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. To preserve the participants' trust throughout the study, rigorous steps were implemented to guarantee that ethical considerations were thoroughly addressed.

The researcher conducted her study with utmost care, ensuring the well-being and rights of participants. They prioritized informed consent, fairness, the minimization of potential harm and the maintenance of confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards were met. The study's execution was meticulously guided by ethical principles, ensuring the participants' rights and well-being were paramount throughout. (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that emphasizes the necessity of treating research participants with dignity and respect while recognizing their autonomy in making decisions about their involvement in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting interviews, the researcher obtained permission from the participants and arranged the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This was done to ensure that the researcher's presence would not disrupt the participants' schedules and to avoid the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

Throughout the research, the researcher established a respectful and courteous relationship with the participants and obtained their permission before recording the conversations. The researcher also allowed the participants to ask questions at any time and maintained the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews and focused group discussion. In addition, participants will have the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. The researcher fostered a positive and respectful environment by building trust with the participants and treating them with courtesy. This ensured the study was conducted ethically and with consideration for their well-being.

Consent is a fundamental aspect of research ethics and serves as a way to show respect to research participants. To ensure ethical research practices, participants and their parents were fully informed about the study's goals and procedures. This was achieved through obtaining both parental informed consent and informed assent from the participants themselves. Written consent forms were signed by both parties, confirming their voluntary agreement to participate in the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Transparency was maintained by sharing the study's results and findings with the participants, keeping them informed throughout the research process (Creswell, 2012).

To maintain ethical standards in the research, the participants were given

letters of permission and consent that outlined the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and make informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who decided not to participate were allowed to leave without any explanations and were assured that their data would remain confidential. The researcher will also inform the participants that they have the rights to be informed of the result of the study. The researcher's adherence to these ethical principles guaranteed the study's responsible and respectful execution.

Beneficence as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees was maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All data files were stored securely and never left in a state that could compromise their integrity (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To adhere to the principle of beneficence, the researcher took steps to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality participants' responses and personal identities. To minimize any potential risks, the researcher personally went to each participant's school to communicate with them. By taking these measures, the researcher was able to ensure the well-being and interests of the participants and demonstrate a commitment to ethical research practices.

Furthermore, the data gathered during this research project was solely employed for the objectives specified in the study's design. However, the findings derived from the study might be distributed or communicated to a wider audience through channels such as presentation to the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentation at conferences, either locally, nationally, or internationally. By disseminating the study's results, the researcher aims to share the findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base in their field of study.

Confidentiality towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard

of participants, several measures were implemented. Participant anonymity was maintained by concealing all personal identifiers. Furthermore, all research materials, including audio recordings, transcribed data, field notes, and digital and physical copies of data, were securely disposed of upon completion of data analysis (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To safeguard the participants' anonymity and adhere to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher implemented a system of anonymized coding for all participant responses. This involved carefully rephrasing any potentially identifying details, such as names, genders, ethnicities, or employment and location information, to prevent any breach of confidentiality. Through this coding process and other protective measures, the researcher ensured that the participants' identities remained secure and their privacy was upheld.

Justice in the conduct of this study was upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants who identified themselves as elementary students under neophyte teachers were respected. The research focused on examining classroom management strategies employed by neophyte teachers, ensuring that no ethical concerns regarding the rights of underage participants were compromised. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Elementary students under neophyte teachers were not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they so choose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, and they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Additionally, justice was ensured by including only relevant statements from participants, directly related to the study's goals. These statements were then meticulously transcribed to maintain accuracy (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013).

Results and Discussion

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of data collected through both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The initial phase focuses on quantitative data, examining the level of classroom management skills among novice elementary teachers and identifying key variables that significantly predict their effectiveness in managing classrooms. The second phase delves into qualitative data, presented in a matrix format. This matrix showcases participant responses regarding their experiences with novice teachers' classroom management practices. It includes a detailed examination of the issues explored, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes, and supporting theoretical perspectives. Finally, another matrix integrates the most significant findings from both the quantitative and qualitative phases, providing a holistic understanding of the research results.

Level of Classroom Management

Classroom Management. Table 2 reveals that neophyte teachers in Davao del Norte's public elementary schools exhibit a high level of classroom management, achieving an average mean score of 4.18. This indicates that the classroom management practices are oftentimes manifested among neophyte elementary teachers. The variable of the study which is the classroom management has four indicators namely: classroom physical condition, classroom discipline, care of routine, and time management.

Classroom Physical Condition. In terms of classroom physical condition, the category mean is 4.13, indicating a high level. This suggests that it is oftentimes manifested among neophyte elementary teachers. Among the items under this indicator, maintains

cleanliness inside and outside the classroom to motivate responsive learning got the highest mean of 4.41 indicating as very high. This means that this is always evident in the way teachers behave. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the looks after proper ventilation and lighting for their learners' comfort and ease with a mean of 3.36. This rating is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the neophyte elementary teachers

Table 2. *Status of Language Learning Strategies*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Classroom Physical Condition		
1. Maintains cleanliness inside and outside the classroom to motivate responsive learning	4.41	Very High
2. Provides wholesome atmosphere which results from an orderly and conducive classroom conditions	3.93	High
3. Provides a spacious and comfortable seating arrangement that will encourage positive learning	4.28	Very High
4. Looks after proper ventilation and lighting for their learners' comfort and ease	3.86	High
5. Arranges and keep instructional tools and materials and furniture in their proper places	4.19	High
Category Mean	4.13	High
B. Classroom Discipline		
1. Uses verbal reinforcement that encourages good behavior and discourage inappropriate behavior.	4.50	Very High
2. Sees to it, that order is maintained in the classroom	4.37	Very High
3. Formulates rules that appreciate the values attained from polite and disciplined class	4.41	Very High
4. Awards merits for good behavior	3.97	High
5. Diminishes hostility by cooperation and providing students with opportunities to experience their independence	4.20	Very High
Category Mean	4.29	Very High
C. Care of Routine		
1. Checks attendance regularly	4.20	Very High
2. Checks activities systematically	4.34	Very High
3. Gives clear and direct instructions for the learners to avoid guessing on what to do next	4.56	Very High
4. Establishes clear expectations, limits, and competencies	4.34	Very High
5. Follow procedures in delivering the lesson	4.54	Very High
Category Mean	4.40	Very High
D. Time Management		
1. Observes proper allocation of time for planned activities of the day	4.17	High
2. Is firm regarding scheduled passing of requirements	2.78	Moderate
3. Models time consciousness	3.87	High
4. Establishes guidelines for easy discussion	4.55	Very High
5. Sets enough time for checking activities	4.04	High
Category Mean	3.88	High
Overall Mean	4.18	High

Classroom Discipline. The participants consistently observed a very high level of classroom discipline, reflected in the category mean of 4.29. This suggests that neophyte elementary teachers consistently demonstrate effective disciplinary practices. Uses verbal reinforcement that encourages good behavior and discourage inappropriate behavior garnered the highest rating with the mean of 4.50, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by. Conversely, the awards merits for good behavior got the lowest mean of 3.97, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the neophyte elementary teachers.

Care of Routine. In terms of care of routine, the category mean is 4.40, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the teachers. The highest rated item gives clear and direct instructions for the learners to avoid guessing on what to do next which has a mean of 4.56 and is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the teachers. While, the checks attendance regularly got the lowest mean of 4.20 and is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the teachers.

Time Management. The time management got the category mean of 3.88, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the neophyte elementary teachers. The item establishes guidelines for easy discussion got the highest mean of 4.55 and is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the teachers. Conversely, the is firm regarding scheduled passing of requirements is the lowest rated item which has a mean of 2.78 and is described as moderate. This means that is sometimes manifested by the teachers.

Significant Difference of Level of Classroom Management among Neophyte Teachers

Reflected in Table 3 is the significant difference of the level of classroom management of neophyte teachers in terms of sex and grade level of the participants. The T-test and ANOVA were used in determining the answer to this question. Since the P-value of the sex is 0.437 which is greater than 0.05, this means that the null hypothesis was accepted. This simply means that there is no significant difference on the level of classroom management among neophyte elementary teachers in terms of sex of the participants.

Moreover, since the P-value of the grade level is <0.001, this means that the null hypothesis measured at the 0.05 level of certainty was

rejected. The result indicates that there is a significant difference on the level of classroom management among neophyte elementary teachers in terms of grade level of the participants.

Moreover, since the P-value of the grade level is <0.001, this means that the null hypothesis measured at the 0.05 level of certainty was rejected. The result indicates that there is a significant difference on the level of classroom management among neophyte teachers in terms of grade level of the participants.

Table 3. *Significant Difference of the Level of Classroom Management among Neophyte Teachers*

Variable	Perception					
	Mean	SD	F-Value*	t-value#	P-Value	Decision at $\alpha=0.05$
Sex	Male	4.20	0.40	0.779*	.437	Accepted
	Female	4.14	0.54			
Grade Level	Grade Four	4.59	0.21	20.343#	<.001	Rejected
	Grade Five	3.94	0.42			
	Grade Six	4.18	0.46			

The Experiences of Elementary Students with Regards to their Neophyte Teachers’ Classroom Management

This research delves into three essential themes that emerged from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with participants. To provide context for the qualitative data analysis, Table 1.2 presents profiles of the participants involved in the study. These profiles were chosen strategically, ensuring that they met specific inclusion criteria. The participants were elementary students in grades 4 to 6, under the instruction of neophyte teachers in public schools within Davao del Norte. The table categorizes the participants based on their gender and grade level.

Further, Table 4 deals on the experiences of the elementary students with regards to their neophyte teachers’ classroom management. The table summarizes the key themes that emerged from the students’ responses, providing insights into their experiences.

Table 4. *The Experiences of Elementary Students with Regards to their Neophyte Teachers’ Classroom Management*

Issues Probed	Core Ideas	Code / Categories	Essential Themes	Theoretical Support
Teaching Pedagogy	Enjoying learning through humor and active participation. Having fun while learning. Finding pleasure in teamwork with supportive instruction. Experiencing happiness and cooperation during group tasks.	Enjoyment of interactive teaching strategy Positive group activity experience	Engagement through active participation	Social Constructivism Theory
Impacts of Teacher’s influence towards student engagement and understanding	Worrying about learning interruptions due to teacher’s frustration. Experiencing teacher’s criticism and extended class time. Facing difficulties in understanding multiplication due to inadequate explanation. Getting zero scores due to lack of understanding Experiencing challenges in understanding English and Mathematics concepts.	Negative impact of teacher’s reaction to misbehavior Frustration due to insufficient or unclear explanations	Influencing student engagement and understanding	Social Cognitive Theory
Effectiveness of establishing classroom rules and expectations	Avoiding making noise and paying attention. Adhering to respectful behavior, academic integrity, and maintaining cleanliness. Being punctual and responsible for cleanliness in the classroom. Having etiquette when communicating. Disciplining through cleaning and scolding. Imposing disciplinary measures through grade deductions and extended time of standing in front. Disciplining through deducting points and reminding to avoid repeating the mistake. Overcoming shyness for oral participation and understanding. Listening actively and taking notes for	Expected classroom behavior Consequences for disobedience Responsibility for learning	Classroom rules and expectations	Pragmatic Classroom Management Theory

studying.

Caring for students through prioritizing safety and encouraging personal hygiene.

Ensuring personal grooming and cleanliness for learning preparation.

Inculcating the importance of personal hygiene and health awareness

Engagement through Active Participation. In the context of classroom management, some experiences experienced by the students are the enjoyment of interactive teaching strategy as well as positive group activity experience. It was mentioned by the participants that with the help of teacher's interactive and supportive strategy, they are more engaged which led them to experiences a more effective learning.

Enjoyment of interactive teaching strategy. This is the first code of the first probed issue. Students shared similar thoughts about the teaching methods their teachers use in class. Elementary students enjoy learning through their teachers' humor while teaching, and them being able to interact.

Similarly, Participant 1 enjoys learning when their teacher is being humorous and when it asks them questions about their lesson. Through these interactive tactics, it enabled the student to enjoy the teaching and learning process as it makes her more comfortable and feel encouraged to participate. This highlights the importance of teacher's strategy that will stimulate students' critical thinking skills, and encourage students to be more curious and enthusiastic about learning.

"Ganahan ko kanang mag ginara si Sir and then kanang mag sige siyag pangutana tungod sa among lesson." (IDI-01)

(I like it when Sir is joking around, and when he keeps asking questions about our lesson.)

Moreover, integrating humorous tactics while teaching enables students to have fun while learning. Through this, their teacher creates a positive atmosphere in the classroom, fostering a sense of camaraderie and encouraging students to feel more comfortable expressing themselves. As what Participant 3 said that:

"Ganahan ko anang mag gara-gara siya, kanang pag mag klase siya kay naay dala gara-gara, maka katawa ka." (IDI-03)

(I like it when he acts silly, when he teaches with funny antics, you cannot help but laugh.)

Positive group activity experience. This is the second code of the first probed issue. IDI and FGD participants imparted that doing group activities gives them pleasure as it allows them to collaborate with their classmates. This highlights the importance of enabling the students to socially interact, providing support and encouragement from peers.

In that sense, Participant 5 found pleasure in teamwork with the supportive instruction of their teacher. It enables her to enjoy group activities as their teacher's support helps them understand the task at hand, boosting their self-esteem and motivation to participate actively in group activities. This emphasizes how supportive atmosphere encourages student engagement and promotes a love for learning.

"Ganahan ko mag group activity kay iyang ginainstruct sa amo tapos dili mi niya pasagdan, iya ming tudluan kung unsaon pagbuhat ni nga activity tapos malingaw mi." (IDI-05)

(I like having group activity because she instructs us and does not leave us alone. She teaches us how to do this activity, and we enjoy it.)

In addition, collaborating with classmates allows students to interact with their peers, fostering friendships and a sense of camaraderie. Through group activities, students can be able to enjoy the sense of shared purpose and accomplishment that comes from achieving goals together. As what Participant 10 said that:

"Mag group activity kay kung mag group activity, tanan among classmate malipayon og magtinabangay." (FGD-05)

(Doing group activity because when we have group activity, all of our classmates are happy and help each other.)

Influencing Student Engagement and Understanding. The in-depth interviews and focus group discussions highlighted the significant role teachers play in shaping student engagement and comprehension. Participants emphasized that teachers' influence directly affects how they participate in learning and how well they grasp the material. If this influence continuously give negative impacts students, teachers may diminish students' motivation, engagement, and self-esteem, leading to declination in academic performance.

Negative impact of teacher's reaction to misbehavior. This is the first code for the second probed issue. From the in-depth interviews, students experienced worrying about learning interruptions due to teacher's frustration, and experienced extended class time and receiving teacher's criticism. This emphasizes how a teacher responds to misbehavior can significantly influence the student-teacher relationship and can impact the overall classroom climate.

Similarly, while demonstrating patience and effective conflict resolution strategies when addressing misbehavior can teach students valuable lessons, it is important to avoid walking out due to frustration with misbehavior. The sudden absence of teachers would disrupt

the learning environment, leaving students without supervision and instruction. It is crucial to seek alternative solutions to address misbehavior while fulfilling their responsibilities to their students. As Participant 5 said that:

“Maguol ko kanang magpabadlong among classmate tapos masuko among Ma’am tapos di na ganahan magtudlo sa amo. Muhawa na siya sa amo kay di na siya gusto’g samok. Muhawa siya sa atubangan, di na siya magtudlo sa amo, pasagdaan ra mi niya.” (IDI-05)

(I am worried when our classmate misbehaves and our teacher gets angry, she no longer wants to teach us. She leaves us because she does not want any fuss. She walks away from us, stops teaching us, and just lets us be.)

Furthermore, students' emotional well-being can be affected by how teachers react to misbehavior. Thus, negative responses from teachers can create a sense of shame, anxiety, or resentment in students. These feelings can undermine their overall well-being and make them feel less connected to the classroom community. As a result, students may become less likely to engage positively with the teacher in the future. Acknowledging that we have different level of sensitivity, it is important for teachers to be careful in their reaction to misbehavior to maintain positive relationships, support students' emotional well-being, model appropriate behavior, and foster a positive classroom climate while addressing underlying issues. As what Participant 2 said that:

“Pa solvebon mi ni Sir sa atubangan nya dugay mi pagawson. Patindugon mi sa atubangan. Muington raman si sir nga ‘kamo sige ramog tabi nyag pasolvebon...’ lupig pa daw bata di kabalo. Mangduko sila, maulaw, maminaw nalang.” (IDI-02)

(Sir would make us solve problems in front, and he would make us stay longer. He would make us stand in front. Sir would just say, ‘you keep on talking but when asked to solve...’, he says they are worse than children who do not know. They will lower their heads, feel embarrassed, and just listen.)

Frustration due to insufficient or unclear explanations. This is the second code of the second probed issue. FGD participants mentioned that they experienced difficulties in understanding multiplication due to inadequate explanation, challenges in understanding English and Mathematics concepts, and getting zero scores due to lack of understanding. This highlights that effective teaching involves ensuring that all students have the opportunity to understand and engage with the material fully.

In connection, Participant 7 finds it difficult to understand multiplication because of insufficient explanation. This results her to develop misconceptions about the concept. Students may form incorrect beliefs or strategies for solving multiplication problems, which can hinder their mathematical development and lead to further confusion down the line.

“Kanang mag multiplication pud kay maglisod pud ko kay di pa gud ipang-explain unsa’y buot pasabot ana.” (FGD-02)

(When we also do multiplication, I struggle because it has not been explained what it means.)

Moreover, ensuring that students are adequately prepared to demonstrate their understanding on the assessment increases the likelihood of success, which can help maintain students' confidence and motivation to continue learning. Thus, it is important that teachers should not overlooked the diverse learning needs and abilities of the students, assuming that all students were ready for the assessment without considering individual readiness or comprehension levels. As what Participant 8 said that:

“Kanang dili pa mi kasabot nya magpapasa na, tanan mi ma zero kay wa mi nakasabot.” (FGD-03)

(When we do not understand yet, but our teacher starts collecting papers, all of us get a zero because we did not understand.)

In addition, Participant 10 shares that they experienced challenges in understanding English and Mathematics concepts despite their teacher’s effort. Factors outside of school, such as the home environment and level of parental support, as well as socioeconomic factors, such as poverty and access to educational resources influenced their academic achievement and ability to understand English and mathematics concepts. Thus, in such cases, it's important for teachers to collaborate with colleagues, specialists, and support staff to identify and address the specific needs of struggling students.

“Sa english kay gamay ra among masabtan. Kung magspelling mi, di ka kabalo kung unsa ang spelling kung english. Usahay pud magmath. Pag biskan unsa na nga math, usahay di na makasabot. Ginapasabot ni ma’am pero usahay maglisod jud mi.” (FGD-05)

(In English, we only understand a little. When we spell, we do not know the spelling in English. Sometimes in math too. If it already involves any other kinds of math, sometimes we cannot understand. Ma'am explains it, but sometimes we really struggle.)

Classroom Rules and Expectations. In the context of establishing classroom rule and expectations, the participants mentioned that they experienced having expected classroom behavior, consequences for their disobedience, responsibility for their learning, as well as experienced being inculcated with the importance of personal hygiene and health awareness. This highlights that by instilling habits of responsibility, self-discipline, and respect for authority, Teachers play a vital role in equipping students with the social and emotional competencies essential for success both in the classroom and beyond.

Expected classroom behavior. This is the first code of the third probed issue. From the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion, students experienced adhering to their teachers’ expected classroom behavior, which makes it easier for their teacher to manage the classroom. This emphasizes that providing clear guidelines for behavior teachers can prevent disruptions, address issues promptly, and maintain a focused learning environment.

Similarly, Participant 2 imparted that their teacher expects them to pay attention during class, and avoid making unnecessary noise. Through this, they are able to have clear communication with their teacher, acknowledging that attention is valuable and that disruptions can hinder the learning experience for everyone in the classroom.

“Dili magsaba kung naay magsturya sa atubangan nya maminaw sa klase” (IDI-02)

(Do not make a noise when someone is speaking in front, listen attentively during class)

Moreover, establishing expectations for respectful behavior, academic integrity and maintaining cleanliness are important for teachers to foster personal growth, and character development among students. It can also significantly contribute to building a supportive, welcoming, and productive learning environment that fosters the overall growth and well-being of every student. As Participant 5 said that:

“Bawal magtabi. Mag renispetohay, dili mag sinundugay sa classmate og kailangan limpyo pirme among classroom.” (IDI-05)

(It is not allowed to keep talking. We should respect each other, copying from classmates is prohibited, and our classroom should be kept clean.)

Furthermore, Participant 6 shared that their teacher expects them to be punctual and responsible for the cleanliness of their classroom. By emphasizing these qualities, teachers help students develop habits and behaviors that they will carry with them beyond the classroom.

“Naay balaod ni ma’am nga dili malate. Hinumduman nga manglimpyo, kung kinsay mauna sa room manglimpyo.” (FGD-01)

(Ma'am has a rule that no one should be late. Remember to clean up, whoever arrives first in the room should clean up)

In addition, politeness in communication is essential for fostering positive relationships and effective communication. It teaches students etiquette and social skills that are valuable beyond the classroom. It helps them navigate various social situations with confidence and grace, preparing them for interactions in formal settings. As what Participant 7 said that:

“Dapat kung mutubag mo kay Ma’am kay naay ‘po/opo’.” (FGD-02)

(When you answer Ma'am, you should use 'po/opo'.)

Responsibility for learning. This is the second code of the third probed issue. IDI participants mentioned that they experienced being encouraged always by their teachers to overcome their shyness for oral participation and understanding, as well as to listen actively and take notes for studying. Through this, teachers help students take ownership of their learning by actively engaging in the learning process, demonstrating initiative, possessing growth mindset, developing the skills they need to succeed academically and beyond.

In connection to this, Participant 2 shared that they experienced being pushed by their teacher to overcome their fears and participate. This allows them to engage with course material in a meaningful way, rather than passively listening to lectures, making them more likely to understand as well as retain the information and concepts.

“Dili maulaw nga mag oral. Ang uban dili kaayo kasabot kay di man kaayo maminaw, pa solvebon niya. Maulaw man ang uban gud kanang mag oral kay basin daw mamali, ingon man si Sir nga wala daw mali nga answer kay usbon raman daw ni Sir kung mali.” (IDI-02)

(Do not be shy to do oral recitation. Some could not understand much because they do not listen attentively, so he asks them to solve. Some are shy to do oral recitation because they think they might make a mistake, but Sir says there is no wrong answer because he will correct it if it is wrong.)

Furthermore, listening actively and taking notes during class are important study habits that promote understanding and retention. It reinforces the idea that learning is an active process that requires effort and engagement, and it empowers students to be accountable of their academic success. As what Participant 4 said that:

“Kailangan maminaw mi, kailangan dili magsaba og magtake-note jud og maayo para naay istudyhon sa balay.” (IDI-04)

(We need to listen, we need not to make noise and take notes carefully so we have something to study at home.)

Consequences for disobedience. This is the third code of the third probed issue. IDI and FGD participants experienced facing consequences for their misbehavior in class. This ensures that students are held accountable for their actions, which helps teachers to instill a sense of responsibility and self-discipline to them. It communicates to students that there are consequences for behavior that disrupts the learning environment or disrespects others.

Similarly, Participant 3 mentioned that they are being disciplined through scolding and making them clean. These are the consequences when they disobey the rules such as no cheating and not making unnecessary noise during class. This highlights that there are various forms of behavior modification, discouraging students from repeating disobedient behavior in the future.

“Palimpyuhon mi tapos mangasaba siya. Masuko ra siya, kung masuko siya pareho anang manundog kay kasab-an niya apil nagpasundog og nanundog. Kanang magsaba mi, muingon siyag hilom nya musunod rapud akong mga classmates.” (IDI-03)

(He would make us clean up and then he scolds us. He just gets angry, and when he does, just like cheating, he will scold both those who copy and let others copy. When we are noisy, he tells us to be quiet and then my classmates will immediately follow.)

Moreover, Participant 6 shared that their teacher impose disciplinary measures through grade deductions and extended time of standing in front. These are the consequences when they don't follow the rules being established by their teacher. These may seem strict, but when implemented appropriately and accompanied by clear explanations and support, they can be effective tools for fostering discipline, accountability, and responsibility among students.

“Kung dili namo tuman ang balaod ni Ma'am kay kami ang makatindog didto sa atubangan, dugay pajud mi palingkuron. Bawasan pajud og grado.” (FGD-01)

(If we do not follow Ma'am's rules, we will be the ones who will be standing in front, and we will also be kept there longer. Grades will also be deducted.)

Additionally, addressing disobedience in a calm and constructive manner fosters a positive and supportive teacher-student bond. It allows both the teacher and students to address the situation rationally and constructively, without escalating tensions. As what Participant 10 said that:

“Bawasan og score og grado. Patindugon sa atubangan og ingnan nga ‘Sunod ayna na ninyo usaba’.” (FGD-05)

(Deduct points from the score or grade. Make them stand in front and tell them, 'Next time, do not do it again'.)

Inculcating the importance of personal hygiene and health awareness. This is the last code of the third probed issue. From the focus group discussion, students experienced being cared through prioritizing their safety and encouraging personal hygiene, as well as ensuring their personal grooming and cleanliness for learning preparation. They are encouraged to do proper hygiene practices to reduce the risk of illness that might lead them to absent.

In connection to this, maintaining good personal hygiene contributes to overall health and well-being. It helps keep the body clean, prevents skin infections, and reduces not just the risk of illness, but also the likelihood of developing hygiene-related health issues such as body odor. As Participant 7 said that:

“Bago sad muanhi diri sa classroom, maligo og magshampoo og mag-ilis og bag-o nga sanina kay para pud sa amua, para limpyo ang among lawas, para dili masakit.” (FGD-02)

(Before coming to the classroom, we should shower, have shampoo, and change clean clothes because it is also for us, to keep our bodies clean, so we will not get sick.)

In addition, when students feel clean and well-groomed, they are better able to focus and concentrate on their studies. Good personal hygiene reduces discomfort and distractions, allowing students to devote their full attention to learning tasks and academic activities. As Participant 10 said that:

“Dapat kung makaabot na sa eskwelahan, makaligo na og makailis na og nilabhan. Kung maabot na si Ma'am sa room, dapat hinlo na, wala nay gubot, og makapamugkot na og buhok.” (FGD-05)

(When you come to school, you should already took a bath, and changed clean clothes. By the time Ma'am arrives in the room, everything should be clean, no mess, and hair should be neatly fixed.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

This research explores classroom management practices of neophyte teachers in Davao del Norte's public elementary schools. It utilizes a mixed methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data to gain a comprehensive understanding. The study's fourth research question focuses on integrating the findings from both data collection phases.

Table 5 presents a comparison of key findings, with each row representing a specific aspect of the study. The first column lists the focal points, while the second and third columns display the quantitative and qualitative results, respectively. The quantitative findings, typically represented by indicators with the highest mean, are compared to the qualitative findings, which highlight identified responses from participants. This comparison aims to confirm or refute the quantitative results. The fourth column describes the nature of this data integration, while the fifth column presents axiological implications derived from the combined findings. Respondents rated the item maintains cleanliness inside and outside the classroom to motivate responsive learning as very high.

Moreover, on care of routine, the specific item which is rated as very high is establishes clear expectations, limits, and competencies. All of these results are connected with the qualitative findings, which under the theme classroom rules and expectations. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative in this aspect.

Table 5. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Aspect Or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature Of Data Integration	Axiological Implications
Classroom rules and expectations	Table 2 on Classroom Discipline item 1 about uses verbal reinforcement that encourages good behavior and discourage inappropriate behavior (M=4.50) which rated as very high.	Table 3 on consequences for disobedience under the theme of classroom rules and expectations	Merging – converging	Neophyte elementary teachers place strong value on giving clear guidelines and consistent feedback in promoting desirable behavior.
	Table 2 on Classroom Discipline item 2 about sees to it, that order is maintained in the classroom (M=4.37), and item 3 about formulates rules that appreciate the values attained from polite and disciplined class (M=4.41), both are rated as very high.	Table 3 on expected classroom behavior under the theme of classroom rules and expectations	Merging – converging	Neophyte elementary teachers shows a strong commitment on creating a conducive learning environment that contributes to the overall development and well-being of the students.
	Table 2 on Physical condition item 1 about maintains cleanliness inside and outside the classroom to motivate responsive learning (M=4.41) which rated as very high	Table 3 on responsibility for learning under the theme of classroom rules and expectations	Merging – converging	Neophyte elementary teachers acknowledge the importance of promoting a sense of ownership over one's education, encouraging proactive engagement in the learning process.
Engagement through active participation	Table 2 on Care of Routine item 4 about establishes clear expectations, limits, and competencies (M=4.34) which rated as very high.	Table 3 on positive group activity experience under the theme of engagement through active participation	Merging – converging	Neophyte elementary teachers reflect the values of supportive instruction, and promoting clarity and confidence in learning through reducing ambiguity, facilitating understanding, and encouraging active engagement.
Influencing student engagement and understanding	Table 2 on Care of Routine item 3 about gives clear and direct instructions for the learners to avoid guessing on what to do next (M=4.56) which rated as very high.	Table 3 on negative impact of teacher's reaction to misbehavior under the theme of influencing student engagement and understanding	Merging – converging	Neophyte elementary teachers display a recognition of the value of time management and its impact on learning outcomes, however suggests a need for a commitment to efficiency, maintaining focus on educational objectives.

Engagement through Active Participation. The specific item on care of routine rated as very high is gives clear and direct instructions for the learners to avoid guessing on what to do next. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under engagement through active participation. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Influencing Student Engagement and Understanding. In quantitative phase, the specific item on time management, observes proper allocation of time for planned activities of the day, is rated high by the respondents. Also, the item models' time consciousness, is rated as high. These results are connected to the qualitative findings under influencing student engagement and understanding. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative in this aspect.

Level of Classroom Management

This section delves into the analysis of the survey's quantitative data. To ensure a comprehensive and rigorous interpretation, the findings are examined within the context of relevant scholarly research and literature. This approach allows for a robust analysis that is grounded in existing knowledge and provides a deeper understanding of the survey results.

Classroom Management. Chapter 3 shows a high level of classroom management effectiveness. This finding suggests that neophyte teachers are perceived by their students as satisfactory or effectively managing their classrooms. This is in congruence with the study of Abid and Ehsan (2021) which highlights that despite the initial difficulties encountered by neophyte teachers, implementing structured classroom management strategies can result in effective classroom management. Essential factors for creating a well-managed environment include clear rules, positive reinforcement, consistent consequences, interactive teaching methods, and strong teacher-student relationships.

Classroom Physical Condition. The classroom physical condition indicator's rating is high according to the results of this study. This result is indicative that the classroom physical condition is regarded by the respondents as satisfactory. actively contribute to a clean and well-maintained learning environment, both inside and outside the classroom, which in turn encourages a more productive and responsive learning experience, and they are comfortable with the spacious seating arrangement they have. This is in accordance with the study of Afalla and Fabelico (2020) which shows that when teachers focus on the physical conditions of the classroom, students are more likely to feel relaxed and comfortable, leading to improved academic performance. This emphasizes that by prioritizing the physical environment, teachers can create an optimal setting that fosters student success.

In agreement with the study conducted by Terada and Merrill (2023) which underscores the importance of incorporating elements like plants, natural lighting, and flexible seating arrangements in classrooms. The research indicated that these factors not just enhanced student well-being but also empowered educators to maintain a more conducive learning environment by lowering stress levels and boosting student satisfaction. This highlights the importance of intentional classroom design in improving the educational environment. By integrating natural elements and flexible layouts, classrooms can become more conducive to effective teaching and learning, benefiting both teachers and students.

Classroom Discipline. The respondents rated classroom discipline as very high. This result suggest that the respondents perceive their teachers as emphasizing classroom rules, minimizing disruptive behavior, and recognizing positive conduct to maintain peace and order in the classroom. This connotes that the respondents find classroom discipline as highly evident on their teacher's classroom management. In agreement with the study conducted by Kursheed (2021) that classroom discipline is a crucial element in teaching. The study illustrates students as water and classroom discipline as the walls of a canal. Just as the flow of water is effectively maintained and distributed when the canal walls are strong, students will perform better when classroom discipline is strict and well-enforced.

Furthermore, Mitchell et al. (2018) supports the notion that effective classroom management necessitates clear expectations, specific feedback, and high response rates, which can be enhanced through comprehensive professional development for educators and systematic strategies. This highlights the importance of discipline in establishing boundaries and standards for student behavior, aiding teachers in their classroom management efforts. It also underscores that by investing in the continuous growth and development of teachers and implementing supportive institutional structures, schools can empower educators to apply evidence-based discipline techniques, cultivating a nurturing and stimulating learning atmosphere for every student.

Care of Routine. This aspect was rated by the respondents as very high. The respondents' answers strongly suggest that they place a high value on routines. Care of routine encompasses the establishment and upkeep of routines for various classroom activities, transitions, and procedures that promote organization, efficiency, and a positive classroom environment. In agreement with Rumlus' (2021) perspective, teaching routines and procedures is essential for developing good skills and behaviors early in education. Classroom routines and procedures are designed to maintain order within the classroom. A child's character is shaped by their habits, attitudes in response to situations, and the language they use with others. A child's habits will develop through daily and repeated actions; initially, these actions may need to be enforced, but over time, they will become second nature.

In line with the argument, Karam (2022) emphasize that classroom routines guide the actions of both teachers and students, instilling confidence, consistency, trust, security, and a sense of protection in students by helping them recognize beneficial patterns. The study indicates that routines simplify a complex environment, clearly outlining what students can expect, what behaviors are expected from them, and what constitutes acceptable conduct. By establishing clear routines, students can effectively manage their daily responsibilities, benefiting both themselves and their teachers. These structured processes streamline transitions between activities, minimizing interruptions and fostering a more productive learning environment. Consistent adherence to routines empowers students to cultivate greater dependability and personal responsibility.

Time Management. The indicator, time management, was rated as high by the respondents. We can infer that time management is oftentimes observed. The students share that time management specifically in establishing guidelines for easy discussion is really evident to their teachers' classroom management, while being firm regarding scheduled passing of requirements is moderately practiced. This is in congruence with the findings of Batool et al. (2023) which emphasized the crucial role of time management for ensuring efficient and effective daily teaching. When teachers are well-prepared for their lessons, they can dedicate more time to instruction. Teachers noted that they uphold classroom schedules, address tardiness, and implement routines to boost students' academic success. However, some elementary teachers take a more lenient approach to deadlines, demonstrating empathy for students facing personal challenges, such as family issues, health concerns, or other external factors.

Moreover, according to the study of Sigdel (2018) which highlight that teaching is increasingly challenging today due to teachers'

negligence regarding classroom time management. Consequently, maximizing the efficiency of classroom time is paramount for teachers, given its limited nature and its significance in the teaching-learning process. This study highlights that modern teachers must balance various responsibilities, such as delivering the curriculum, assessing students, managing the classroom, and handling administrative tasks. Ineffective time management can make these responsibilities overwhelming, resulting in heightened stress and reduced efficiency.

Significant Difference of Level of Classroom Management among Neophyte Teachers.

Sex. The findings of this study revealed that there is no significant difference between the student's sex in their perceptions about the level of classroom management among their neophyte teachers. The findings of this study challenge the conclusions reached by Darkwa et al. (2020) regarding gender disparities in student perceptions of classroom management. The study uncovers a marked difference in the way sex influences perceptions of students. While both sexes recognize the importance of task orientation, male students consistently rate their teachers higher in areas like fostering a sense of unity among students, providing support, actively engaging them, and promoting collaboration. Conversely, female students place a greater emphasis on the teacher's ability to effectively guide and structure learning activities. These findings highlight the distinct perspectives that boys and girls bring to their understanding of a positive classroom environment.

Furthermore, Korpershoek et al. (2018) challenges the results of this study, suggesting that distinct leadership approaches can influence student outcomes and overall well-being. Notably, their findings highlight the unique reactions of male and female students to different management styles. The study reveals that Male students tend to respond positively to structured and authoritative management, showing better academic and behavioral outcomes. Female students, however, thrive in environments that provide emotional support and foster positive teacher-student relationships, rating these teachers more highly.

Grade Level. This research discovered a notable disparity in how students from different grade levels perceive classroom management practices employed by neophyte teachers. In agreement with the research conducted by Mitchell & Bradshaw (2019) which states that younger students rate their teachers higher when they employ proactive and positive management techniques such as setting clear expectations, using positive reinforcement, and maintaining a supportive classroom environment, while, older students are more sensitive to the fairness and consistency of classroom management practices. This research highlights how various classroom management and discipline approaches influence students' views on the learning environment. It specifically examines how these perceptions differ based on the students' grade levels.

Moreover, multiple research studies, including the work of Pianta et al. (2018), consistently demonstrate a significant correlation between students' grade levels and their views on classroom management. This connection, in turn, impacts their level of engagement in the learning process. The study shows that students in higher levels are more engaged where they have some degree of autonomy over their learning and where teacher-student relationships are built on mutual respect and understanding. These findings emphasize how classroom management strategies influence student engagement across different grade levels.

The Experiences of Elementary Students with Regards to their Neophyte Teachers' Classroom Management

The experiences of elementary students with regards to their neophyte teachers' classroom management was shown in the previous chapter. The study explored a range of issues, generating a diverse set of core concepts that were subsequently categorized. This approach aimed to gain deeper insights into the experiences of elementary students regarding classroom management by neophyte teachers. To provide context, the study drew upon diverse perspectives from educational theorists and authors, incorporating their insights into the analysis.

Engagement through Active Participation. The findings in this study reveal that this can be seen in their experiences in their classroom that they find enjoyment in interactive teaching strategy as well as positive group activity experience. This result finds support in the Social Constructivism Theory, proposed by Vygotsky (1968). According to this theory, knowledge built through social interactions and collaborative activities, rather than being passively absorbed. The idea also posits the importance of active learning, where students are not passive recipients of information but actively engage in the learning process. It suggests that collaborative learning, involving interaction with peers and teachers, is crucial for optimizing learning outcomes. This collaborative approach not only fosters cognitive development but also makes learning more enjoyable.

Moreover, the present finding further strengthens the study made by Ovcharova (2023) through highlighting the importance of teachers' skills in creating and maintaining a stimulating learning environment towards the effectiveness of the students' educational process. The study focused on how teachers can create a dynamic learning environment where students actively participate and engage in the classroom, centering on the teacher's role in fostering this kind of active learning. It shows that teachers who employ various strategies in fostering students' active involvement and engagement addresses students' cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects.

Influencing Student Engagement and Understanding. A study revealed that students experienced impacts of their teachers' influence towards their engagement and understanding. This finding supports the idea that people learn through both personal experiences and by watching others, as outlined in Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986). This theory suggests that individuals acquire knowledge and skills not only from their own actions and their outcomes, but also by observing the behaviors of others and the results of those

behaviors. This suggests that the behaviors and attitudes of teachers can significantly influence students' learning processes. If teachers demonstrate negative behaviors or attitudes, such as a lack of enthusiasm, unfairness, or poor communication, students may emulate these behaviors, resulting in reduced engagement and understanding.

Consequently, the present finding supports the notions put forth by Kuril et al. (2021) that while positive teacher behaviors are recognized as enhancing student engagement, when teachers exhibit negative behaviors, student engagement suffers. This link is further complicated by students' own learning strategies, specifically their cognitive and metacognitive skills. Additionally, how students approach challenges, known as their mastery goal orientation, also plays a role in this connection. The findings highlight the importance of equipping teachers with knowledge about the impact of their behavior on student learning, particularly on student engagement.

Classroom Rules and Expectations. The findings revealed that students experienced having established expected classroom behavior, consequences for their disobedience, responsibility for their learning, as well as experienced being inculcated with the importance of personal hygiene and health awareness. This observation is in line with the Pragmatic Classroom Management Theory of Wong and Wong (2009), which highlights the crucial role of establishing well-defined rules, procedures, and expectations in fostering a conducive learning environment. A key tenet of this approach is that teachers should proactively set clear expectations from the outset, laying the groundwork for a structured and productive learning experience. This approach not only reduces disruptive behavior but also fosters a positive learning environment where students comprehend their responsibilities. Students are more likely to be actively involved in their education or learning when they understand the guidelines and potential outcomes.

Furthermore, this finding aligns with Alter and Haydon's (2018) study, which highlights the frequently recognized problem of teachers, particularly those early in their careers, in effectively managing student behavior. Thus, the current study underscores the importance of clearly defined classroom rules as a cornerstone of effective classroom management. These rules provide a simple and proactive framework for preventing disruptive behavior by establishing clear expectations and consequences. The study's findings emphasize two critical elements of effective classroom rules: explicitly communicating the rules to students and consistently linking them to appropriate positive or negative consequences.

Data Integration of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The findings from both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of the study converged at each key point of analysis, providing a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. With this, axiological implications were developed specifically classroom rules and expectations, engagement through active participation, and influencing student engagement and understanding.

Classroom Rules and Expectations. Classroom rules and expectations lay the foundation for an effective and enriching educational experience through promoting a structured environment, fostering a sense of community, and encouraging positive behavior. The study by Leach and Helf (2018) highlights that the primary goal of consequences should be to reduce problem behaviors and encourage positive ones. Creating a system of positive consequences for following classroom rules and procedures, along with clear expectations and rewards for good behavior, can significantly improve student conduct. This approach can minimize or even eliminate the need for disciplinary actions. While some students may require additional support based on their individual needs, implementing a consistent system of positive consequences for all students can greatly reduce the number who need further behavioral intervention.

Consequently, this connection is supported by the study of Jimerson (2022) which explored the impact of a modern classroom behavior management approach, known as the Raising Lions method, on minimizing disruptive behaviors. This method emphasizes prompt teacher responses, a positive or neutral communication style, and concise cues that empower students to regulate their behavior and re-engage in learning without fear of reprimand. Overall, the results show that The Raising Lions method significantly decreases disruptive behavior in elementary classrooms, with the most notable impact stemming from teachers refraining from labeling the behavior and offering brief action prompts for self-reflection and self-correction.

Engagement through Active Participation. Both quantitative and qualitative findings reveal that students with supportive instruction, enabled them to have clarity and confidence in learning, encouraging them to actively engage. This finding conforms to the work of Etal (2021) that providing clear instructions and strategies to enhance oral communication is particularly important for neophyte teachers as they refine their teaching practices. Clear oral instruction contributes to effective classroom management by helping students understand the objectives, actively engage, and take responsibility for their academic journey.

Moreover, the study of Boonstra et al. (2020) reveals that teachers who employ motivating teaching behaviors, such as providing support and guidance, can greatly enhance student engagement during lessons. In lessons where students were highly engaged, teachers were observed to start with a lot of energy and then, after around ten to fifteen minutes, switched their focus to getting students actively involved by giving them chances to try things out and offering help as they worked.

Influencing Student Engagement and Understanding. Both quantitative and qualitative findings reveal that teacher's reaction to misbehavior sometimes impacts instructional time for the entire class. According to Hampton (2021) student disruptions can create a ripple effect throughout the classroom, leading teachers to feel compelled to address each instance of misbehavior immediately, which results in considerable loss of instructional time. On average, teachers report losing about 144 minutes per week to managing classroom behavior and disruptions, equivalent to roughly three weeks of the school year. When teachers devote too much attention to correcting

misbehavior, it negatively impacts instructional time.

Furthermore, the study of Ghasemi (2024) revealed that student misbehavior is a major source of occupational stress that affects teachers' engagement in counterproductive workplace behaviors. Such misbehaviors elicit negative emotional responses from teachers, and these negative feelings mediate the relationship between student misbehavior and teachers' counterproductive actions, which can diminish their performance, particularly concerning instructional time.

In addition, according to the study of Wegrzyn (2022) teachers frequently encounter diverse and unexpected situations, and reducing student misbehavior allows them to engage in mindfulness activities that enhance student learning. When teachers spend more time addressing behavioral issues, students miss out on valuable instructional time. By minimizing the need for corrections, teachers can dedicate more time to providing learning opportunities.

Conclusions

The data analysis leads to the following conclusions:

The level of neophyte teachers' classroom management is very high in terms of classroom discipline and care of routine, which indicates that these indicators are always manifested by neophyte teachers. While, in terms of classroom physical condition and time management, neophyte teachers were rated as very high which indicates that the indicators are oftentimes manifested.

The findings highlighted a notable disparity in classroom management skills among neophyte teachers when categorized by sex and grade level. The analysis, employing T-tests and ANOVA, indicated no significant variation in classroom management effectiveness based on sex. Conversely, a significant difference was observed in classroom management proficiency among neophyte teachers when grouped by the grade level they taught.

The qualitative data was analyzed thematically, drawing insights from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. This analysis revealed valuable information about how elementary students perceive and interact with their novice teachers. The findings highlight a range of experiences that influence student engagement, learning, and behavior in the classroom. The following themes were emerged: Engagement through Active Participation, Influencing Student Engagement and Understanding, and Classroom Rules and Expectations.

To gain a deeper understanding of how neophyte teachers manage their classrooms, the study's qualitative findings were analyzed thematically. This analysis aimed to corroborate the quantitative results. The insights from both phases were then integrated, aligning with the study's design. The quantitative data revealed that the level of classroom management among neophyte teachers aligned with the insights derived from the qualitative phase. The findings from both quantitative and qualitative research suggest that despite the initial difficulties of being a neophyte, teachers can demonstrate remarkable levels of classroom management which create structured, supportive, and engaging learning environments that benefit their students both academically and personally.

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